

The Influence of Financial Distress, Profitability, and Leverage on Tax Avoidance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the effect of financial distress, profitability, and leverage on tax avoidance in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2022–2024 period. Tax avoidance is proxied using the Cash Effective Tax Rate (CETR). This research uses a quantitative approach with panel data regression analysis through the Random Effect Model (REM), processed using EViews software.

The results show that financial distress has no significant effect on tax avoidance, suggesting that financially distressed companies do not necessarily adopt aggressive tax planning strategies. In contrast, profitability and leverage both have a positive and significant effect on tax avoidance, indicating that highly profitable firms and those with higher debt levels are more likely to engage in tax avoidance.

The adjusted coefficient of determination (Adjusted R²) shows that the three variables explain approximately 12.16% of the variation in tax avoidance, with the remaining percentage explained by other factors not included in the model. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring profitable and highly leveraged firms to minimize potential tax revenue losses.

I. INTRODUCTION

Taxation plays a vital role in the structure of state revenue, significantly contributing to national development and public welfare. According to Law Number 17 of 2003 on State Finance, taxes are classified as one of the primary sources of state financing through the national budget (APBN). Alongside national economic recovery, Indonesia's tax revenue has shown a positive trend in recent years. After surpassing the target in both 2022 and 2023—amounting to IDR 1,716.8 trillion (115.6%) and IDR 1,867.9 trillion (108.8%) respectively—the government set a tax revenue target of IDR 1,988.9 trillion for 2024. However, by the end of 2024, the actual tax revenue stood at IDR 1,932.4 trillion, or 97.2% of the target.

Although this reflects a 3.5% increase compared to the previous year, the shortfall in achieving the target indicates that there is still untapped potential in state revenue. This further highlights that tax avoidance remains a critical challenge within the national taxation system. The implementation of the self-assessment system, which grants taxpayers—particularly corporations—the autonomy to calculate and report their tax obligations, may inadvertently

create opportunities for legal tax avoidance practices that ultimately reduce state income.

Year	Tax Revenue Target (in Trillion IDR)	Actual Revenue (in Trillion IDR)	Tax Achievement Percentage (%)
2021	1,229.6	1,277.5	103.9%
2022	1,485.0	1,716.8	115.6%
2023	1,718.0	1,869.2	108.8%
2024	1,988.9	1,932.4	97.2%

Source: State Budget Report, Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia (www.kemenkeu.go.id).

Tax avoidance refers to a strategy employed by taxpayers to legally reduce their tax obligations by taking advantage of gaps, loopholes, or imperfections in the prevailing tax regulations. While this practice does not violate the law directly, it often sparks debate from ethical and fiscal policy perspectives due to its potential to erode government tax revenues (Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). The implementation of a self-assessment system in Indonesia further increases the

risk of such behavior, as it allows companies the discretion to calculate and report their tax liabilities independently—opening wider opportunities for legal yet detrimental tax avoidance practices.

In Indonesia, tax avoidance has drawn significant attention from the government as it undermines the tax base that should rightfully be collected. To measure the level of tax avoidance, proxies such as the Cash Effective Tax Rate (CETR) or Book-Tax Difference (BTD) are commonly used, as they capture discrepancies between accounting income and taxes actually paid in cash (Dyreg et al., 2008).

Several internal financial factors are thought to influence a firm’s inclination toward tax avoidance, including financial distress, profitability, and leverage. Financial distress represents a condition in which a company experiences significant financial pressure, particularly in meeting short-term liabilities such as current debts and interest payments. This can be triggered by declining revenues, sustained operating losses, or failure to manage fixed cost burdens (Platt & Platt, 2002). In such circumstances, management may turn to tax avoidance strategies as a means to conserve cash (Swandewi & Noviari, 2020). While legally permissible, this practice remains controversial as it can negatively impact state revenue. Tax avoidance in times of financial strain may also be interpreted as a survival tactic to preserve liquidity and avoid liquidation, especially when alternative financing sources are limited.

However, prior research has produced mixed results. Studies by Swandewi & Noviari (2020) and Destira & Nenda (2025) found a positive relationship between financial distress and tax avoidance, implying that companies under financial pressure are more likely to engage in such practices. On the contrary, Riantami & Triyanto (2018) and Pratiwi et al. (2021) observed a negative relationship, suggesting that financially distressed firms may avoid aggressive tax strategies due to the potential legal risks and damage to their fiscal reputation.

Meanwhile, profitability reflects a company’s efficiency in generating income. The higher the profitability, the larger the tax burden incurred (Sari & Nugroho, 2020). As a result, management may be incentivized to implement tax planning strategies to reduce tax expenses and maintain earnings stability (Dwiyantri & Jati, 2019). The relationship between profitability and tax avoidance also shows varied findings. Some studies, including Novriyanti & Dalam (2020) and Swandewi & Noviari (2020), found a positive effect, indicating that more profitable firms are more inclined toward tax avoidance. Conversely, studies by Setiawan & Darmawan (2021) and Hidayat & Sopian (2025) reported no significant relationship, which implies that highly profitable companies may avoid tax avoidance if they are governed by strong ethical frameworks or operate in tightly regulated sectors.

Leverage, on the other hand, reflects the extent to which a firm utilizes debt to finance its operations. A high level of

leverage indicates greater reliance on debt financing. In tax terms, interest on debt is considered a deductible expense, which reduces taxable income. Therefore, the higher the interest expense, the lower the reported taxable income and, consequently, the lower the tax liability (Puspita & Febrianti, 2018). This opens the door for firms to legally minimize tax payments by adjusting their capital structure—essentially a form of tax avoidance. Several studies, including those by Riskatari & Jati (2020) and Taufik & Muliana (2021), identified a positive and significant relationship between leverage and tax avoidance, suggesting that firms with higher debt levels are more likely to engage in tax planning strategies.

Nevertheless, not all research supports this view. Octaviani & Sofie (2018) reported a negative effect, while Hidayat & Sopian (2025) found no significant relationship between leverage and tax avoidance. These inconsistent findings highlight a research gap that warrants further investigation.

In response to this, the present study focuses specifically on manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2022–2024 period. The objective is to provide updated empirical evidence on the influence of financial distress, profitability, and leverage on tax avoidance. This research is motivated by inconsistencies in previous findings, where some studies found significant relationships while others did not. The results of this study are expected to enrich the tax accounting literature and offer practical insights for tax authorities in formulating more effective policies to detect and deter corporate tax avoidance behavior.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Agency Theory

This research is grounded in Agency Theory, as introduced by Jensen and Meckling (1976). The theory explains the relationship between the owners (principals) and managers (agents) of a company, where conflicts of interest may arise due to differing objectives. Managers, having more access to internal information than the owners, may engage in actions that benefit themselves. In the context of taxation, managers may choose to engage in tax avoidance to reduce tax liabilities, preserve net income, and potentially increase their own compensation—even if such actions may not align with the owners’ or the government’s best interests (Watts & Zimmerman, 1986).

Tax Avoidance

Tax avoidance refers to efforts made by taxpayers to legally reduce their tax obligations by exploiting loopholes or ambiguities in tax laws. Although not illegal, the practice is often viewed negatively because it reduces potential state revenue (Siburian & Siagian, 2021). According to Aryotama and Firmansyah (2019), tax avoidance differs from tax

evasion in that it remains within legal boundaries, but may still raise ethical and fiscal concerns.

Financial Distress

Financial distress refers to a condition in which a company experiences difficulty in meeting its financial obligations, such as being unable to pay debts or suffering continuous losses. In such cases, firms often implement cost-efficiency strategies, including efforts to reduce tax liabilities through tax avoidance, as a means of ensuring business continuity (Nadhifah & Arif, 2020). Common predictive models for measuring financial distress include the Altman Z-score and Springate models.

Profitability

Profitability is an indicator of how efficiently a company generates profit. Firms with higher profitability are subject to higher tax burdens, which may motivate management to engage in tax planning strategies, including tax avoidance, to maintain stable after-tax earnings (Dwiyantri & Jati, 2019). However, several studies such as Pakpahan & Masyitah (2023) suggest that profitability is not always significantly associated with tax avoidance, depending on each firm's strategy and governance structure.

Leverage

Leverage indicates the extent to which a company relies on debt financing compared to equity. A higher leverage ratio suggests greater dependency on debt. In tax terms, interest payments on debt are categorized as deductible expenses, which reduce taxable income and, consequently, the tax burden (Puspita & Febrianti, 2018). Therefore, firms with high leverage have a greater potential to engage in tax avoidance strategies (Sinaga & Suardikha, 2019).

The Effect of Financial Distress on Tax Avoidance

Financial distress represents a condition of significant financial pressure, where companies may struggle to meet obligations such as debt payments or may incur ongoing losses. Under such circumstances, management is likely to implement cost-saving measures, including the reduction of tax expenses through tax avoidance strategies (Swandewi & Noviari, 2020).

According to agency theory, managers, acting in their own interests, may engage in tax avoidance to preserve cash flow and stabilize earnings when faced with financial distress. Destira & Marliani (2025) found that financial distress positively influences tax avoidance, suggesting that firms under financial pressure are more inclined to avoid taxes. However, Pratiwi & Adnyana (2021) found no significant relationship, highlighting an existing research gap.

H₁: Financial distress affects tax avoidance.

The Effect of Profitability on Tax Avoidance

Profitability is a key indicator of a company's ability to generate earnings. Firms with high profitability face higher

tax obligations, which can prompt management to engage in tax avoidance to reduce tax expenses and maintain stable net income (Dwiyantri & Jati, 2019).

From the agency theory perspective, managers are motivated to report favorable financial performance to maintain investor confidence. Thus, in times of high profits, tax avoidance becomes a legitimate strategy to preserve firm value. Swandewi & Noviari (2020) found a positive relationship between profitability and tax avoidance, while Pakpahan & Masyitah (2023) found no significant effect, highlighting the presence of conflicting findings.

H₂: Profitability affects tax avoidance.

The Effect of Leverage on Tax Avoidance

Leverage represents the company's reliance on borrowed funds to finance operations. A higher leverage ratio implies a greater interest expense, which is deductible from taxable income and can thus lower tax liabilities (Puspita & Febrianti, 2018).

From a tax planning perspective, companies with high leverage may use debt strategically to reduce their fiscal burden. Studies such as Pakpahan & Masyitah (2023) have found that leverage has a positive effect on tax avoidance. Conversely, Hidayat & Sopian (2025) reported no significant relationship, again pointing to inconsistent empirical evidence.

H₃: Leverage affects tax avoidance.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Type of Research

This study is a quantitative associative research with a causal approach. According to Sugiyono (2018:15), quantitative research is based on the philosophy of positivism and is used to examine specific populations or samples with the objective of testing hypotheses. Data collection is conducted using research instruments, and the analysis is carried out statistically to evaluate the relationships between variables.

The purpose of this study is to empirically examine the effect of financial distress, profitability, and leverage on tax avoidance, making the use of a quantitative approach highly relevant in order to obtain objective, measurable, and generalizable findings.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2018:117), a population is defined as a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that possess certain characteristics and qualities determined by the researcher to be studied and from which conclusions are drawn. Based on this definition, the population in this study includes all manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the period 2022 to 2024.

The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling method based on

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specific criteria. The criteria applied in this research are as follows:

1. Manufacturing companies that were consistently listed on IDX during 2022–2024.
2. Companies that published audited annual financial statements for all three years.
3. Companies that provide the necessary data to calculate the research variables:
 - Tax avoidance (CETR)
 - Financial distress (Springate Score)
 - Leverage (Debt to Equity Ratio)
 - Profitability (Return on Assets)
4. Companies that were not delisted, suspended, or merged during the observation period.

Type and Source of Data

This study uses secondary data in the form of annual financial statements published by each company. The data were obtained from the following sources:

1. The official website of the Indonesia Stock Exchange: www.idx.co.id
2. The official websites of the respective companies
3. Other financial sources such as RTI Business, Yahoo Finance, and similar platforms.

Operational Definition and Variable Measurement

Variable	Formula / Indicator	Description
Tax Avoidance (Y)	$CETR = \frac{\text{Cash Tax Paid}}{\text{Pre-Tax Income}}$	The lower the CETR, the higher the level of tax avoidance
Financial Distress (X1)	$\text{Springate Score} = 1.03X_1 + 3.07X_2 + 0.66X_3 + 0.4X_4$	A score below 0.862 indicates that a company is in financial distress
Profitability (X2)	$\text{Return on Assets (ROA)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	Indicates the efficiency of the company's asset utilization in generating profit
Leverage (X3)	$\text{Debt to Equity Ratio (DER)} = \frac{\text{Total Liabilities}}{\text{Equity}}$	Reflects the proportion of debt to equity (capital structure)

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

This study employs panel data regression using the Random Effect Model (REM) approach. The estimation is conducted using the EGLS method (Swamy and Arora estimator). The results are presented as follows:

Dependent Variable: CETR

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)

Date: 07/01/25 Time: 09:52

Sample: 2022 2024

Periods included: 3

Cross-sections included: 30

Total panel (balanced) observations: 90

Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficien			
	t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.281241	0.022649	12.41711	0.0000
FD	0.343063	0.126926	2.702854	0.5083
ROA	0.514862	0.235380	2.187368	0.0314
DER	0.263896	0.119208	2.213750	0.0295

Effects Specification			
	S.D.	Rho	
Cross-section random	0.044019	0.2902	
Idiosyncratic random	0.068850	0.7098	

Weighted Statistics			
	Mean	dependent	
R-squared	0.121570	var	0.177010
Adjusted R-squared	0.090927	S.D. dependent var	0.073520
S.E. of regression	0.070098	Sum squared resid	0.422581
		Durbin-Watson	
F-statistic	3.967316	stat	1.830683
Prob(F-statistic)	0.010638		

Unweighted Statistics			
	Mean	dependent	
R-squared	0.116418	var	0.264111
		Durbin-Watson	
Sum squared resid	0.581732	stat	1.329843

- The R^2 value of 0.12157 indicates that the three independent variables collectively explain only 12.16% of the variation in tax avoidance (CETR).
- The probability value of the F-statistic is 0.010638 (< 0.05), which means the regression model is statistically significant, suggesting that the independent variables jointly influence tax avoidance.
- The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.83, which is close to 2, suggests the absence of autocorrelation in the residuals, supporting the model's validity.

Effect of Financial Distress on Tax Avoidance

The analysis shows that the variable financial distress (FD) has a positive coefficient of 0.343063, but with a probability value of 0.6083, which is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that although firms experiencing greater financial pressure may be more inclined toward tax avoidance, the relationship is not strong enough to be statistically confirmed.

This finding is consistent with studies by Pratiwi & Adnyana (2021) and Hidayat & Sopian (2025), which suggest that financially distressed companies do not necessarily engage in tax avoidance. These companies often

face stricter compliance requirements, greater audit scrutiny, and reputational risks, making aggressive tax strategies less appealing. Therefore, financial distress may not be a key determinant in a firm’s tax planning behavior.

Effect of Profitability on Tax Avoidance

The variable profitability (ROA) exhibits a positive coefficient of 0.514862 with a p-value of 0.0314, indicating a positive and significant influence on tax avoidance. This means that firms with higher profitability tend to be more inclined to engage in tax avoidance strategies.

According to agency theory, managers of highly profitable firms have incentives to maintain strong net earnings through tax planning measures such as tax avoidance (Dwiyanti & Jati, 2019). These strategies help preserve shareholder confidence and may also enhance managerial compensation. The results align with findings from Swandewi & Noviyari (2020), reinforcing the notion that profitability is a relevant driver of tax avoidance behavior.

Effect of Leverage on Tax Avoidance

The variable leverage (DER) has a positive coefficient of 0.263896 and a p-value of 0.0295 (< 0.05), indicating a positive and statistically significant relationship with tax avoidance. This suggests that firms with higher debt ratios are more likely to engage in tax avoidance strategies.

This finding supports the trade-off theory, which states that interest expenses from debt reduce taxable income, thereby lowering tax obligations (Puspita & Febrianti, 2018). Companies with highly leveraged capital structures can legally utilize interest deductions as a means of tax efficiency. The result is in line with previous research conducted by Pakpahan & Masyitah (2023) and Swandewi & Noviyari (2020).

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of this study examining the effect of financial distress, profitability and leverage on tax avoidance among manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2022–2024, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Financial distress does not have a significant effect on tax avoidance.

Although theoretically, companies facing financial difficulties are expected to seek ways to reduce their tax burden, this study finds that financial distress—measured using the Springate model—does not significantly influence tax avoidance in a statistical sense.

2. Profitability has a positive and significant effect on tax avoidance.

The higher a firm’s profitability (as measured by ROA), the greater its tendency to engage in tax avoidance. This behavior is likely motivated by

management’s desire to maintain stable after-tax earnings through effective tax planning strategies.

3. Leverage has a positive and significant effect on tax avoidance.

Firms with higher levels of debt tend to be more actively engaged in tax avoidance strategies. This is largely driven by the tax advantages of interest expenses, which are deductible and thereby reduce the firm’s taxable income.

4. The regression model is statistically significant overall.

However, the R-squared value of 12.16% indicates that the three independent variables in this model explain only a small portion of the variation in tax avoidance. Therefore, it is suggested that other factors not included in this model may also play a role and should be explored in future research.

Based on the findings and the limitations of this study, several recommendations are proposed as follows:

1. For the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT):
It is important to strengthen the monitoring and oversight of companies with high leverage and profitability levels, as both factors were found to significantly influence tax avoidance practices. The DGT may utilize publicly available financial data as an early detection tool to identify corporate taxpayers with a high potential for engaging in tax avoidance.
2. For Company Management:
Management should ensure that tax planning strategies are carried out in a legal and ethical manner. Although tax avoidance is legally permitted, overly aggressive practices may pose reputational risks and negatively impact the company’s image over the long term.
3. For Future Researchers:
It is recommended to:
 - Incorporate additional variables such as corporate governance, firm size, independent commissioners, or fixed asset intensity, which may offer better explanatory power regarding tax avoidance behavior.
 - Utilize a longer observation period or include non-manufacturing sectors for broader generalizability.
 - Consider adopting dynamic panel data approaches or alternative econometric models that can address issues of endogeneity.

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